

Cloud Computing in Agricultural Zone

Sulu George
AJCI7MCA-1055
Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirapally
sulugeorge@mca.ajce.in

Dr Juby Mathew
Assistant Professor
Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirapally
jubymathew@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract-Cloud computing is a community-focused environment that relies on sharing informations, storage, provider, programs & different vital computing sources. In modern-day generation of cloud computing era very helpful for centralized the all-agricultural related statistics financial institution (Soil & associated, weather, research, Crop, Farmers, Agriculture advertising and marketing, fertilizers and pesticide statistics) inside the cloud.

Lots of cloud computing companies have emerged up and there is a large boom within the usage of this provider.. Google, Microsoft, IBM and Amazon have began imparting cloud computing services. The future development of agriculture depends how the new technologies consisting of cloud computing are followed with a focal point on farmer wishes. The use of this technologies should help a farmer in terms of accessibility. Latest technological development has through a drastic change in every field and agriculture is no other practices to it. Cloud computing generation impacted sincerely on agriculture area and related services they offer for customers. on this paper, also talk Computing model, characteristics, deployment model, cloud agro model, cloud advantages and assignment of cloud computing in agriculture field.

Keywords: Cloud computing, Structure, IaaS, Paas & SaaS

INTRODUCTION:

Statistics and applications are being swept up from computing device desktops and company server rooms and hooked up in "the compute cloud". In extensive, there's a shift in the geography of computation. What is cloud computing exactly? As a starting here's a definition "An rising laptop paradigm wherein informations and offerings live in hugely scalable information facilities withinside the cloud and may be taken from all related gadgets over the network".

An Increasing Development of IT and communications and boom of information sizes withinside the community, collectively with the emergence of recent programs and computing wishes, ability and implements is exponentially Day-by-Day. Cloud computing is a brand new method which brings the data computing and garage from PCs into large information centre, In those data wishes as offerings via Internet. On the alternative hand, the 0.33 character wishes to do his computational necessities, carrier efficiency, garage ability and growing the reliability in Agricultural area. This generation is fantastic sizable to enhance agricultural subject construction, the mixture of agricultural data and modernization.

OBJECTIVE:

The goal of this paper is hence dealing with the idea of cloud Computing, its powerful implementation and it is able to make contribution a critical position in growing the rural sectors withinside the growing areas.

CLOUD COMPUTING:

Cloud computing is a device to make computer associated offerings to be had in a easy way covering the complexities of these offerings, without clearly understanding and getting involved in the technicalities of ways. Cloud computing comes into consciousness best whilst we reflect about what IT has always wanted - a manner to boom ability or upload distinct abilities to the modern putting at the fly without investing in new infrastructure, schooling new employee or licensing new software. Here 'at the fly' and 'without making investment or schooling will becomes the keywords in the modern scenario. But cloud computing gives a higher solution.

The attraction of cloud computing is that the offerings can be taken every time and anywhere wanted. It additionally decreases the free of taking the ones offerings. At the identical time, it offers participation of very much less manpower and conservation of those offerings. It also makes customers loose from sure worries such as buying software, preserving them up-to-date, preservation of information etc. All these troubles could be taken care of by Cloud providers.

Main cloud computing models are:

- **Software as a Service (SAAS):** It is a complete operating environment with applications, management and the user interface. The application is provided to the client through a thin client interface and the customers responsibility begins and end with entering and managing its data.
- **Platform as a Service (PAAS):** Provides cloud platforms and runtime environment for developing, testing and managing applications. It allows software developers to deploy applications without requiring all the related infrastructure.
- **Infrastructure as a Service (IAAS):** It is a cloud service that provides basic computing infrastructure services are available on pay-for-what-you-use model. And it is a service provider that manages all the infrastructure while the client is responsible for all other aspects of the deployment.

Figure-1: Basic Cloud computing shape

KEY FEATURES

Among all the cloud computing functions, following 3 functions had been observed to be the middle of uplifting cloud computing to the modern stage, consistent with a survey completed amongst 250 agencies.

Figure -2: Modules of cloud computing

The figure shows the current nature of cost of cloud computing offerings globally. It exactly shows the public cloud offerings annual boom charge from 2020 to 2022.

Figure-3: Value of cloud computing offerings

ENHANCEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF INDIA

To save all the informations in a common cloud platform. It clearly shows the cloud versions to fulfill the needs of the user in a efficient way.

1. **Cloud Agro System:** This part of the gadget may be used to monitor the general functionalities of the gadget and render the wanted offerings. In order to give those offerings, the Agro gadget have the subsequent offerings:

- **Demand-deliver:** It can give an updated image of the modern call for and deliver data of agro merchandise in distinct components of the country.
- **Communication:** Literacy charge of India is (with city India at 86% and rural at 71%), consistent with The Economic Times. It shows that most of city populace are illiterate farmers. Therefore, the gadget will offer offerings in their native language.
- **Communication Devices:** The gadget includes mobile phone offerings and enables the farmers in obtaining data from e-information bank from any location, at any time, through mobile.
- **e-Knowledge sharing:** The gadget also keeps provision to have online verbal exchange with the consultants and attend online schooling applications using the Community Service Centres as the local data bases.
- **Conducting Research:** It will assist the country wide and worldwide researchers to extract Indian agricultural information without delay from the e-information bank.

2. **e-Data Bank:** It is a imperative information bank and it can be used to save all the agriculture associated data in a centralized cloud. In order to do so, the e-data bank includes the subsequent databases:

- ✓ **Crop associated data:** It takes data associated to all the crops grown in recent past in different locations. This will help the local farmers of different areas of the nation in crop related selection.
- ✓ **Weather information:** It stores the climate information and also the weather conditions for a particular period. It will gain the farmers in selection making associated to selection of vegetation.
- ✓ **Soil Information:** Soil data also performs position in crop associated selection making. So, this section affords information on nature of soil of different locations. It can also offer the trend of soil in past and will forecast the destiny of soil.
- ✓ **Growth development racking:** It monitors information on crop boom in many areas on a ordinary period. This may be especially beneficial in evaluating the crop growth area base and also evaluating it with clear picture.

- ✓ **Farmers Data:** It takes the area level farmer associated information, to monitor the participation of local farmers in Indian agricultural area. It will assist the coverage makers in designing Indian agricultural policies.
- ✓ **Expert Consultation:** It affords to problems that farmers mostly experience. It can also have a right to publish unattended issues seeking for answers from the experts.

THE PROPOSED CLOUD AGRO SYSTEM

Related on the above said gadget, this paper denotes the coming model to put into effect cloud computing in Indian agricultural area :

Figure-4: cloud agro gadget

BENEFITS OF THE SUGGESTED MODEL

The cautioned model, if carried out properly, will gain all the concerned areas to a fantastic extent.

- **Data control:** The data may be controlled by the carrier provider, a group of experts. That ensures a higher and prepared control of information.

- **Data readiness:** The model affords data from the e-data bank databases to its stakeholder at all time and at any location.
- **Local and global Communication:** The model makes the verbal exchange between users plenty quicker , less complicated and inexpensive.
- **Rural-urban migration:** A principal trouble of India is rural-urban migration. It can be minimized as the model affords its offerings all over the regions.
- **Security:** It affords an stronger safety as the assets may be saved in cloud and may be managed commonly by the carrier providers. Thus, it is not a reason of subject for its customers.

PREDICTION USING WEKA TOOL

Data mining enables to extract delicate data end result from a extend of data which offers an correct cost on the data search. several machine getting to know algorithms are used for mining facts.system mastering classifies each facts into supervised ,unsupervised, semi-supervised and strengthen-ment mastering in this paper,the purpose is to investigate the climatic rate in a particular period and are expecting the modern scenario of the people.

STEPS IN DATA ANALYZING

The main steps included in analyzing data includes:

- Dataset Preparation
- Dataset Preprocessing

In Dataset preparation we create an excel sheet with th following attributes: Outlook ,temperature, humidity,windy corresponding class for a particular period.

The next step is to create the corresponding CSV file of the Dataset. CSV(Comma Separated Value) format will lay the data in a table of rows and columns and a comma is used to separate values on a row. After creating the CSV file , we will convert the corresponding file into arff file(Attribute Relation File Format).

The classified data will use the Precision and Recall Values to compare and analyze the climatic variations.

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FP})$$

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN})$$

IMPLEMENTATION STEPS

Figure-5: Download and install weka tool

Figure-6: Processing of data in Weka

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	outlook	Temperat	Humidity	Windy	Play	States
2	sunny	hot	high	FALSE	no	kerala
3	sunny	hot	high	TRUE	no	tn
4	overcast	hot	high	FALSE	yes	andhra
5	rainy	mild	high	FALSE	yes	rajasthan
6	rainy	cool	normal	FALSE	yes	tripura
7	rainy	cool	normal	TRUE	no	goa
8	overcast	cool	normal	TRUE	yes	delhi
9	sunny	mild	high	FALSE	no	gujarat
10	sunny	cool	normal	FALSE	yes	punjab
11	rainy	mild	normal	FALSE	yes	sikkim
12	sunny	mild	normal	TRUE	yes	meghalaya
13	overcast	mild	high	TRUE	yes	assam
14	overcast	hot	normal	FALSE	yes	mp
15	rainy	mild	high	TRUE	no	telagana
16						

Figure-7: Prepare dataset and convert into .csv file

Figure-8: Applying Naïve Bayes classification algorithm to the dataset

The analysis have been carried out with the help of Naïve Bayes Classification which showed the result as :

TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall
0.654	0.571	0.196	0.265

Classification using Random Forest

Classified Instances	8	62.1519 %
Incorrect Instances	6	38.9571 %
Kappa statistic		0.0567
Mean absolute error		0.4227
Root mean squared error		0.3889
Relative absolute error		94.7361 %
Root relative squared error		106.8404 %
Total Number of Instances	16	

Classification Using Random Tree

humidity = high

| outlook = sunny : No (3/0)

| outlook = overcast : Yes (2/0)

| windy = TRUE : no (1/0)

humidity = normal

| outlook = sunny : yes (2/0)

| outlook = overcast : yes (2/0)

|| temperature = hot : no (0/0)

|| temperature = mild : yes (1/0)

|| temperature = cool

||| windy = FALSE : yes (1/0)

||| windy = TRUE : no (1/0)

Size of the tree : 16

It can be used to predict if the climate will be proper or bad.

Naive Bayes classifier plays higher than different models with much less training data if the idea of independence of function holds. If you had categorical input values, the Naive Bayes algorithm plays fairly properly in contrast to numerical variables.

FEATURE STATISTICS IN ORANGE

Inputs:Data: input data.

Outputs:Reduced data: table containing only selected features, Statistics. The feature facts affords a short manner to analyze and discover abilities in a information .

Figure-9: Feature statistics

1. Info at the present day facts set length and number and sorts of functions
2. The histograms on the proper may be coloured by way of any feature. If the chosen feature is categorical, a discrete colour palette is used (as shown in the example). If the given function is numerical, a non-stop color palette is used. The table on the proper includes records approximately each function in the information set.

BOX PLOT USING ORANGE

- Data: input dataset
- Selected Data: instances selected from the plot
- Data: data with an additional column showing whether or not a factor is selected The container Plot widget indicates the distributions of attribute The **Box Plot** widget gives the distributions of attribute values. It is a great exercise to test new infor-

mation with this system to speedy discover any anomalies, consisting of duplicated values (e. g, gray and grey), outliers.

- Stretch bars: Shows values (proportions) of data instances. The unticked box shows absolute values.
- Display field labels: display discrete values above every bar.
- Sort by subgroup frequencies: Sort subgroups by their descending frequency.

by corporation. India will certainly benefit if the proposed model is implemented effectively in the rural quarter. This could bridge the space between generation, information and farmers of India.

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Figure-10: Blox plot

CONCLUSION

The Cloud computing is a recreation converting segment of IT that is not only impacting the manner computing offerings are and may be brought but also the way in which customers will use IT. In Indian agricultural area, the cautioned system-can be taken as a pilot project. An powerful development of this system will inspire different sectors also, which will lead to desirable gain of transferring closer to cloud. This will virtually have a nice effect in the overall economic growth of the nation. Cloud computing is a newly delivered idea and almost all of the growing countries are not ready to accept and put into effect it. This will in go back result in a well-connected world. Cloud computing will aid the farmers get right of entry to to utility offerings at any anywhere the use of numerous terminals. They request their resources from the cloud now not from set bodily entity. Within the subsequent 3 years, cloud computing in India might be increasingly more utilized